

The role of open metadata in the SSH scholarly communication – current challenges in the context of the TRIPLE project

Agenda

- GoTriple and metadata ecosystem in the SSH.
- GoTriple stakeholders and their patterns of interaction with the service:
 - providers and users,
 - information services,
 - knowledge creators,
- Focus on information services and knowledge creators:
 - advanced data providers,
 - metrics,
- Challenges for metadata FAIR-ification.
- How to address expectations?

Fig. 1. Bibliographical Data Landscape in the Humanities (report by DARIAH-ERIC's Bibliodata WG. Source: [Zenodo](#)).

Open metadata ecosystem – Computations

SSH specificity

Metadata aggregators – stakeholders

- metadata aggregators key stakeholders
 - data providers (data sources) and online users,
 - **information services:**
 - other aggregators,
 - service providers (metrics, indexes, etc.),
 - **data-driven knowledge creators:**
 - bibliometrics,
 - scientometrics,
 - cultural analytics.

Open metadata – discovery

Source: <https://project.gotriple.eu/triple-in-the-eosc/>

Open metadata – discovery

Computations

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Open metadata – knowledge

Streamgraph of feminism

570 most relevant documents Data source: GoTrip... 1 Jan 1750 - 26 Jan 2023 Document types Data quality More information

Overview (570 documents)

Search within visualization... show: Any sort by: Relevance

journal/newspaper article

Feminismo afrodiaspórico. Una agenda emergente del feminismo negro en Colombia ; Afro-diaspolar feminism. An emerging agenda for black feminism in C... (2014-06-01)

Aurora Vergara Figueroa, Katherine Arboleda Hurtado
Universitas Humanistica, Iss 78, Pp 109-134 (2014)
[doi]: <https://doi.org/10.11144/javeriana.UH78.fafn>

Afro-diasporic Feminism. An Emerging A genda of Black Feminism in Colombia Abstract In this paper we reflect on the motivations, agenda and commitments set within the context of the first international seminar "Afro female Conspiracy: Rethinking feminisms from diversity" hel...

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Sémiotique de l'enterrement prématuré : le féminisme à l'ère du postféminisme ; Premature burial Semmiotic: feminism in the era of postfeminism (2018-06-01)

Mary Hawkesworth
Glad, Vol 4 (2018)
[doi]: <https://doi.org/10.4000/glad.1065>

This essay investigates the strange coincidence of the unprecedent...

Report an Issue

Open metadata – knowledge

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Knowledge Map of feminism

100 most relevant documents Data source: GoTrip... 1 Jan 1750 - 26 Jan 2023 Document types Data quality More information

Overview (100 documents)

Search within visualization... show: Any sort by: Relevance

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Area: [Hisphilso, Amina mama, Bodies](#)

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Open metadata – knowledge

Table 2. The top two DH journals by the number of publications for the DH levels exclusively and significantly

Database	Exclusively		Significantly	
	1st	2nd	1st	2nd
Crossref	LLC (1,944)	CHum (1,555)	AI&S (1,468)	CL (951)
Dimensions	RIDE (797)	LLC (653)	AI&S (1,000)	CL (728)
Microsoft Academic Graph	LLC (602)	RIDE (416)	D-Lib (946)	CL (914)
Scopus	CHum (1,123)	LLC (550)	LRE (994)	AI&S (860)
WoS	RIDE (529)	LLC (339)	CL (673)	LRE (420)

Fig. 1: Early modern authors¹⁷ who published the most titles on history according to the ESTC catalogue data; the highlighted authors are compared further below.

Lahti, L., Ilomäki, N., & Tolonen, M. (2015). A Quantitative Study of History in the English Short-Title Catalogue (ESTC), 1470-1800. *LIBER Quarterly: The Journal of the Association of European Research Libraries*, 25(2), 87–116. <https://doi.org/10.18352/lq.10112>

Gianmarco Spinaci, Giovanni Colavizza, Silvio Peroni, A map of Digital Humanities research across bibliographic data sources, *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, Volume 37, Issue 4, December 2022, Pages 1254–1268, <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqac016>

GoTriple for information services

UNIVERSITY OF WROCLAW

GoTriple for knowledge creation

For whom?

SCIENCE
EUROPE

The
Alan Turing
Institute

HUMANITIES
&
DATA SCIENCE

GoTriple as a SSH dataset and its data services

More:
<https://zenodo.org/record/7568873#.Y9g6S3bMK5c>

Challenges (some of them)

1. limitations of providers' metadata quality and interoperability of their services,
2. dispersion of metadata resources and its impact on the ability to properly monitor and shape the aggregation scope,
3. specificity of SSH (meta)data – cultural heritage impact, role of bibliodiversity and multilingualism,
4. providing proper and sustainable infrastructure to support complex and diverse data.

Addressing needs and expectations

Providers of open metadata in the SSH need support in FAIR-ification of metadata:

- persistent identification,
- linked open data infrastructures,
- standardisation and harmonisation,
- metadata generation and access to innovations (ML, AI).

Typical challenge for aggregators:

Only when this support is provided, operationalised and sustainable the GoTriple dataset can – in the long run – provide additional value for information services and knowledge creators.

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Conclusions

1. GoTriple – as the go-to metadata aggregator for the SSH – is a discovery system, but also a specific type of dataset with potential to contribute great value to other information services and knowledge creators.
2. To do so, GoTriple needs good quality, open SSH metadata.
3. SSH (meta)data providers need a systemic and sustainable support to improve (meta)data quality.
4. (Go)Triple and OPERAS consortium are in a proper position to offer this support and can very easily showcase its relevance for the scholarly communication.

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Follow us on:

TRIPLE
service

*The **GoTriple** platform will be the
Discovery Service of the OPERAS
Research Infrastructure.*

OPERAS
open access in the european research
area through scholarly communication

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Tomasz Umerle, Agnieszka Karlińska

tomasz.umerle@ibl.waw.pl,
agnieszka.karlinska@ibl.waw.p

visit us at: <https://computations.eu>
